

NIMHD Research Framework Adaptation: Common Circumstances Before Firearm Suicide Deaths Among Black Adults

Most suicide deaths involve firearms.¹ However, rates of suicide using firearms have been rising faster among Black American adults than non-Hispanic white, Hispanic, American Indian/Alaskan Native, Native Hawaiian/Pacific Islander, and Asian American adults.² This suggests the presence of a health disparity – a preventable difference in the burden of firearm suicide deaths experienced by Black adults – culminating in the deaths of over 9,000 Black adults from 2018-2022.

Using narrative data from a large sample of all Black adult decedents from 2013-2021, our recent study summarized the personal challenges Black adults often experience before dying by firearm suicide.^{3,4} In this brief, we present an initial adaptation the *National Institute on Minority Health & Health Disparities (NIMHD) Research Framework* focusing on firearm suicide deaths among Black adults in the U.S., organizing our findings by domain and level of influence.

However, additional research is needed to investigate which factors contribute to this deadly health disparity. It is our hope that this working adaptation will inform and motivate new research and be further developed and adapted over time.

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References:

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		LEVELS OF INFLUENCE			
		Individual	Interpersonal	Community	Societal
DOMAINS OF INFLUENCE	Biological	Biological Vulnerability & Mechanisms (medical diagnoses, mental health diagnoses, comorbidity)	<i>Intergenerational mental ill-health, intergenerational trauma, grief from death of loved ones</i>		
	Behavioral	Health Behaviors (stopping treatment, past suicidal attempts) Coping Strategies (substance use)	Family Functioning (infidelity, passionate arguments, domestic violence, gradual deterioration of relationships, child custody disputes)	Community Functioning (<i>exposure to community violence</i>)	Criminal justice practices
	Physical/Built Environment	Firearm accessibility		Community Environment (easy access to purchasing, stealing, or borrowing firearms) Community Resources (<i>access to racial/ethnic minority clinicians</i>)	<i>Public health surveillance system inequities (e.g., under/misreporting of Black suicide deaths)</i>
	Socio-cultural Environment	Sociodemographic Factors (unemployment, bankruptcy, criminal justice history/involvement) Individual Cultural Factors (attitudes on firearm rights)		Community Norms (<i>Historical traumas manifested in community norms</i>) Community Structural Discrimination (<i>public stigma on suicide</i>)	Social Norms (<i>Black tradition of arms, societal firearm culture</i>) Societal Structural Discrimination (<i>cultural discrimination, public stigma on suicide</i>)
	Healthcare System	<i>Medical mistrust, mental health beliefs, past treatment experiences, insurance coverage, healthcare cost for treatment</i>	<i>Patient-provider relationships, power dynamics, misdiagnosis, clinician cultural competency/awareness, clinician bias</i>	<i>Clinician norms and hesitation to conducting firearm safety and lethal means counseling</i>	<i>Public mental health and healthcare workforce initiatives in Black communities, availability of mental health services</i>
Health Outcomes	Population Health				

Notes: This is a working adaptation of the NIMHD Research Framework focusing on firearm suicide death among black adults in the us. **Bold** headings were included from the original framework and the version adapted for mental health disparities (Alvidrez & Barksdale, 2022). The non-bold, non-italicized text represents factors identified through the data analyzed in Goldstein (2024) and Goldstein & Sanger (2025). The italicized text represents postulates and interpretations extending from the analyzed data. Blank cells (and missing bold headings found in the original frameworks) indicate areas not addressed through the source data. As such, the authors hope that this working adaptation will inform and motivate new research, and they intend for this framework to be further developed, filled in, and adapted over time.